

МЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ КАРТЫ КАК СРЕДСТВО РАЗВИТИЯ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ

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MENTAL MAPS AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING OF HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена использованию ментальных карт (mind maps) как эффективного инструмента для развития критического мышления у студентов высших учебных заведений, особенно в технических направлениях. В статье авторы исследуют различные аспекты и преимущества ментальных карт, включая их роль в структурировании и систематизации информации, что способствует более глубокому пониманию и анализу учебного материала. Применение ментальных карт помогает развивать аналитические способности, креативное мышление и самостоятельность студентов, что важно для их адаптации в условиях информационного перенасыщения и быстроменяющегося общества.

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the use of mind maps as an effective tool for the development of critical thinking among students of higher educational institutions, especially in technical areas. In the article, the authors explore various aspects and benefits of mental maps, including their role in structuring and systematizing information, which contributes to a deeper understanding and analysis of educational material. The use of mental maps helps develop analytical abilities, creative thinking and independence of students, which is important for their adaptation in conditions of information oversaturation and a rapidly changing society.

Ключевые слова: визуализация; критическое мышление; ментальная карта; образование; высшее образование; учебный процесс.

Keywords: visualization; critical thinking; mental map; education; higher education; educational process.

I. Introduction

Modern education strives not only to impart knowledge, but also to develop in students the skills necessary to successfully adapt to a rapidly changing world. One of these key skills is critical thinking, which allows you to analyze information, draw informed conclusions, and make rational decisions. In the context of a digital society and the rapid development of technology, critical thinking becomes especially important for students in higher education, especially in technical fields. Students must have the skills of analysis, critical evaluation of information, as well as the ability to think independently in conditions of information oversaturation and a rapidly changing environment.

The mind maps method is an effective tool for developing critical thinking. Mental maps are visual diagrams that allow you to structure and systematize information. This method, developed by Tony Buzan, allows you to visualize the relationships between ideas, which promotes deeper understanding and analysis of educational material.

The introduction of mental maps into the educational process of students of higher educational institutions contributes to the development of their analytical abilities, creative thinking and independence. Mind maps help students organize information and highlight key ideas and relationships, which improves their ability to critically evaluate data and arguments.

The purpose of this research is to examine the effectiveness of using mind maps as a means of developing critical thinking in higher education students.

II. Literature review

2.1. Critical thinking

Critical thinking is defined as the ability to actively and systematically process information, draw informed conclusions, and make decisions based on logic and rationality. Critical thinking took its origins in ancient times, during the times of Socrates and Plato. In the early twentieth century, John Dewey, one of the founders of the concept of critical thinking, defined it as “reflective thinking” that involves the active, persistent and careful consideration of beliefs or assumed forms of knowledge in the light of the reasons on which they are based and the conclusions to which they are based, which they lead.

Critical thinking is an important skill that helps you analyze information, make informed decisions, and solve problems. Research [3,5,6,15] notes the relevance of the problem of developing critical thinking among university students.

For example, in work [3], the authors analyze various interpretations of the concept of “critical thinking” in pedagogy, psychology and philosophy.

Work [15] emphasizes the importance of critical thinking as a necessary quality for a modern specialist. The authors note that students who can think critically about information can effectively process multiple perspectives and come up with creative solutions to problems. In the information society, employers require specialists to respond quickly and creatively to emerging tasks, which makes critical thinking a key skill for professional growth. The article examines various technologies and methods aimed at developing this skill in students.

The works [2,7,8,9,12,14,16] provide innovative methods that promote the development of critical thinking among university students.

Work [2] describes methods for the development and formation of critical thinking, such as “Brainstorming”, the “Discussion” technique and “Interrupted case”. The authors also emphasize the importance of technology for systematizing material by drawing up clusters and mental maps, where the main semantic units of the text are presented in the form of diagrams or drawings. These methods promote a structured and deep understanding of information, allowing you to identify key ideas and make connections between them, which is important for the development of critical thinking.

The research [16] presents the role of project activities as a didactic method aimed at developing cognitive activity in students.

The work [14] discusses problem-based learning methods as an effective tool for developing critical thinking in students. The article focuses on the practical application of problem situations in the educational process, which promotes the active involvement of students and the development of their ability to critically evaluate information and make informed decisions.

The work provides recommendations for the use of project activities in the context of developing critical

thinking among students. Zakirova M.R. notes that with the development of research skills, students develop skills of critical thinking, independent search for information and analysis, the ability to solve problems, and also generate new knowledge [7].

The problem of developing critical thinking is becoming increasingly important not only in the educational sphere, but also in social and professional activities. According to research by the World Economic Forum [19], as well as international documents [17, 18], critical thinking is a major component of the modern educational system.

These documents note that critical thinking includes the ability to analyze, think intelligently and interpret information, which is important for working effectively in a rapidly changing society. In addition, employers are increasingly looking for specialists capable of analytical thinking and adaptation in a constantly changing information environment. The World Economic Forum's Future of Jobs report [19] highlights that critical thinking is one of the top five most in-demand skills for 2023. Thus, the importance of developing critical thinking in the context of digital transformation is due to the need to train qualified and adaptive specialists for successful work in the information society.

2.2. Mind Maps as a Tool for Developing Critical Thinking

The development of critical thinking is one of the key tasks of modern education. In recent decades, many studies have been conducted on various methods and tools to facilitate the development of this skill. One such tool is mental maps, which, as studies have shown [4,10,11,13], can significantly improve students' ability to analyze and synthesize information.

The mind map method was developed by Tony Buzan in the 1970s. His first goal was to take notes as quickly as possible and make sure those notes stood out. Due to this specificity, mind maps have the ability to improve knowledge production, classification, sorting, organization and categorization of brain skills. Mind maps are diagrams in which a central idea is surrounded by related sub-ideas that form a hierarchical structure. Buzan argues that mind maps help you use your brain more effectively, improving memory, creative thinking, and organizing information.

The article [4] presents the advantages and methods of using mental maps in the educational process, which help improve the assimilation of material and the development of analytical skills among students of pedagogical specialties. The work of M. Zakirova [10] explores the use of chronological schemes (timelines) to improve the perception and structuring of educational material, which helps students better understand and remember the sequence of events and processes. Work [11] discusses the use of mental maps to stimulate creative thinking and creativity in students, emphasizing their role in visualizing information and improving cognitive processes.

The mind map method allows students to diagram information instead of writing it in sentences, and provides the ability to condense a huge amount of information onto a single page, allowing students to easily

update information at a glance. The mind-map technique simplifies complex text and allows you to structure a large volume of material, making it visually attractive and understandable.

Research shows that mind maps are an effective tool for developing critical thinking in higher education students. They help improve analytical and synthetic abilities, develop creative thinking and increase the motivation and independence of students. The introduction of mental maps into the educational process of technical universities can significantly improve the quality of education and prepare students to solve complex problems in a rapidly changing digital society.

III. Research methodology

The research was conducted at the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi among students in the field of "Professional education in the field of ICT." The purpose of the research was to evaluate the effectiveness of using the mind map method for developing critical thinking in students.

The research involved 35 second, third and fourth year students in the field of "Professional education in the field of ICT".

The research was conducted over one semester and included the following stages:

- Conducting preliminary testing for the level of critical thinking;
- Teaching students methods of creating and using mental maps;
- Introduction of mental maps into the educational process (use of mental maps for analysis, structuring educational material, preparing projects, solving practical problems, etc.)
- Conducting final testing on the level of critical thinking.
- Comparison of pretest and posttest results to assess changes in the level of critical thinking.

A questionnaire was used to assess the level of critical thinking. The survey included questions about

the perception of the mental maps method, their impact on the learning process, and students' personal feelings about using this tool.

IV. Results and discussion

A questionnaire was used to assess the level of critical thinking. The survey consisted of 6 questions to which students answered on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 was "completely disagree" and 5 was "completely agree."

The table shows data from a survey of students about the perception of the mental map method, their impact on the learning process and personal feelings from using this tool.

The survey results showed:

1. Structuring information:
 - Most students (29 out of 35) agreed or strongly agreed that mind maps helped to better structure information;
2. Highlighting key ideas and relationships:
 - The majority of students (29 out of 35) are positive about the impact of mind maps in highlighting key ideas and relationships;
3. Analysis skills:
 - 26 out of 35 students noted that the mental map method improved their skills in analyzing educational material;
4. Creative thinking:
 - 26 out of 35 students believe that the use of mind maps contributed to the development of their creative thinking.
5. Original and innovative solutions:
 - 22 out of 35 students noted that they were able to come up with more original and innovative solutions to problems thanks to mind maps.
6. The benefits of learning how to create mental maps:
 - Almost all students (32 out of 35) found learning how to create and use mind maps helpful

Table I.

Results of a survey on questions about the effectiveness of the mental map method

Questions	Answer options				
	<i>completely disagree</i>	<i>don't agree</i>	<i>neutral</i>	<i>agree</i>	<i>completely agree</i>
1. Mind maps helped to better structure information	1	2	3	15	14
2. The use of mind maps helped to better highlight key ideas and relationships.	0	1	5	17	12
3. The mind map method improved my skills in analyzing educational material.	2	3	4	16	10
4. Mind Maps Helped Develop Creative Thinking	1	2	6	14	12
5. I began to come up with more original and innovative solutions to problems thanks to mind maps.	3	3	7	13	9
6. Learning how to create and use mind maps was helpful.	0	1	2	18	14

The results of the research confirm the hypothesis that the mental map method is an effective tool for developing critical thinking among students of technical universities.

Students demonstrate improved analytical and synthetic abilities, as well as better problem solving

performance, after using mind maps. In addition, the use of mind maps promotes the development of meta-cognitive skills such as planning, monitoring and evaluating one's own thinking.

In addition, the use of mental maps has a positive effect on students' motivation and independence. Students working with mental maps note an increase in interest in the educational material and a desire to research topics more deeply.

V. Conclusions

The research confirmed that the method of mental maps is an effective tool for developing critical thinking among students of technical universities. Mental maps help improve students' analytical and creative abilities, increase their motivation and involvement in the learning process. The introduction of this method into educational practice significantly improves the quality of training of specialists in a rapidly changing digital society.

Main conclusions of the research:

- Mind maps help students organize and structure information, which is an important aspect of critical thinking. Visualizing the relationships between ideas promotes deeper understanding and retention of material.
- Visualization of material based on mental maps stimulates creative thinking, as it contributes to the generation of new ideas and non-standard solutions.
- Working with mental maps makes the learning process more interactive and interesting, which increases student motivation

Thus, the introduction of mental maps into the educational process of technical universities is a promising direction for improving the quality of education and preparing students to solve complex problems in a rapidly changing digital society. The research highlights the importance and effectiveness of mind maps as a tool for developing critical thinking, and suggests considering the possibility of their wider use in educational practice.

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